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EFFECT OF ELECTRONIC BANKING SERVICES ON CUSTOMERS' SATISFACTION IN COMMERCIAL BANKS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract: The study examined the effect of electronic banking services on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was unknown as such the sample size of the study was determined with the aid of Topman's non-parametric sample size determination formula, applied when the population frame is unknown. A sample size of 368 respondents was used for the study. The instruments used for data collection was 'Effect of Electronic Banking Services on Customers' Satisfaction Questionnaire (EEBSCSQ). The instruments were subjected to face and content validation by three experts. The questionnaire was administered twice within an interval of two weeks and the same result was achieved. Two sets of responses were correlated with the use of Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient and 0.77 was obtained. This was considered high enough to make the instrument reliable. Mean rating and paired sample t-test statistics was used for data analysis. The study revealed that mobile banking and point of sale services has a positive and significant effect on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. The study concluded that electronic banking services have a positive and significant effect on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study recommended that banks should give high priority to customers' service delivery and consider mobile banking as important key drivers towards successful implementation of customers' service delivery. It is therefore important that banks constantly improve and upgrade their e-banking system's security in order to reduce the security threat to the system.

Keywords: Electronic banking services, customers' satisfaction, commercial banks

Introduction

The advent of Internet, electronic commerce, communication technology and users' response to this technology has opened opportunity for many businesses including the financial institution (Ismail & Alawamleh, 2017). Adoption of electronic banking service delivery is fast gaining ground in Nigeria. Different e-Banking channels such as electronic cards, internet banking and mobile banking services have been introduced. Online banking is

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the emerging issue, which is expanding rapidly in banking industry especially in African countries. In recent times, banking activities in Nigeria have increasingly depended on the development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Rising numbers of financial institutions are introducing and expanding their offerings of electronic banking products (Ismail & Alawamleh, 2017).

The introduction of Universal banking practice in Nigeria and the adoption of electronic banking by deposit money banks have offered increased services to customers. This is as a result of rapid technological progress and development in the financial market (Ozuru et al., 2016). There is faster delivery of information from the customer and service provider, thus differentiating Internet enabled electronic banking system from the traditional banking operation (Singhal & Padhmanabhan, 2018). This transfer process makes money to be carried in information storage medium such as cheque, credit cards, and electronic means than its pure cash form. E-banking has thus become important channel to sell products and services; leading to a paradigm shift in marketing practices, resulting in high performance in banking sector.

In the past few years, Nigerian banks and generally the financial services industry embraced electronic banking, which has been made possible by the advancements in information technology (IT). Arya (2019) distinguished between three levels of electronic banking platforms. The first level is the basic informational website that introduces the bank as an institute and describes all the services provided. The second level is a website that allows customers to send in applications for services and have access to various information regarding personal accounts. However, these websites do not allow any monetary transactions. The third level of websites or platforms will allow their clients the freedom to make monetary transactions, arrange payments for their bills, and perform online purchases. The latter is the ultimate e-banking platform that gives customers complete freedom to interact and supervise their personal accounts without having to refer back to the banker. Thus, it is possible to distinguish between an informational website/platform and a transactional one.

The level of satisfaction in e-banking is an important aspect to consider because it underlines the engagement of Nigeria bank customers in online banking. Satisfaction is not an easy concept to define because of the different criteria that are involved. Satisfaction, in general, is often linked to the perception that customers had of the product or service before purchasing and the performance after using said product or service (Kotler & Keller, 2018) which would have an impact on customer loyalty and developing trust. When it comes to satisfaction of e-services, studies found a consistent correlation between the quality of services provided and customer satisfaction (Asiyanbi & Ishola, 2018). Lebanon has a relatively low level of satisfaction that can be justified by its low percentage of bank customers that have an electronic account (45%) and engaging in electronic activities (15% having credit cards and 16% using it for bills and purchases) (Digital, 2020). Had the level of satisfaction been higher, these figures would considerably higher since customer satisfaction would expand the clientele base for said products or services (Merhi et al., 2019).

The adoption of electronic banking (e-banking) has brought major challenges to the banking industry in terms of risk exposure. The volume of deposits has increased as well as the fraudulent practices experienced by Nigerian banks since its adoption in the economy. Another challenge is the ability to adopt global technology to local requirements the ability to strengthen public support for e-finance, the ability to keep the confidentiality, integrity

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and authentication of the institution (Jayshree, 2013 in Ekienabor et al., 2018). E-banking has created many new challenges for bank management and regulatory and supervisory authorities. They originate not just from increased potential for cross border transactions but also for domestic transactions based on technology applications which raise many security related issues (Ekienabor et al., 2018).

Despite the existence of some studies on electronic banking services and customer satisfaction in Anambra State, Nigeria, It is a grace period where banks can reexamine their model of operation to come up with better services and solutions that will restore the public's trust in the banking sector. Having no access to the physical banks has been a huge imposition for bank clients, so it can provide an introduction for electronic banking which, in turn, will help the banks maximize the efficacy of their procedures. These shortcomings have somehow contributed to the knowledge gap in literature, thus warranting a more systematic and comprehensive study of the effect of electronic banking services on customer satisfaction. Base on the foregoing, the study evaluated the effect of electronic banking services on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of electronic banking services on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. The specific objectives include:

1. Ascertain the effect of mobile banking on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.
2. Find out the effect of point-of-sale service on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study.

1. What is the effect of mobile banking services on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State?
2. What is the effect of point-of-sale services on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses stated in null form guided this study.

1. Mobile banking services has no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.
2. Point of sale services has no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.

Methods

The study was carried out in commercial banks in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was unknown as such the sample size of the study was determined with the aid of Topman's non-parametric sample size determination formula, applied when the population frame is unknown. A sample size of 368 respondents was used for the study. The instruments used for data collection was 'Effect of Electronic Banking Services on Customers' Satisfaction Questionnaire (EEBSCSQ). The instruments were

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subjected to face and content validation by three experts. The questionnaire was administered twice within an interval of two weeks and the same result was achieved. Two sets of responses were correlated with the use of Cronbach’s Alpha Reliability Coefficient and 0.77 was obtained. This was considered high enough to make the instrument reliable. Mean rating and paired sample t-test statistics was used for data analysis.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the effect of mobile banking services on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean rating of respondents on the effect of mobile banking services on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State

S/n	Item statements	N	Mean (\bar{X})	Decision
1	It increases financial security	270	3.48	Agree
2	Privacy can be easily maintained	270	3.41	Agree
3	It explains the cost of service being used	270	3.37	Agree
4	Transfer of fund is easier	270	3.25	Agree
5	Transfer of funds is faster as compared to manual banking system	270	3.43	Agree
Cluster Mean			3.39	Agree

Analysis in Table 1 showed the mean ratings of respondents on the effect of mobile banking services on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. The analysis indicated that mobile banking services increases financial security, maintain privacy, explain cost of services, easy and fast transfer of funds with the mean ratings of 3.48, 3.41, 3.37, 3.25 and 3.43 respectively in satisfying customers in commercial banks in Anambra State. The findings revealed that respondents agreed that mobile banking services with the cluster mean rating of 3.39 has a positive effect on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the effect of point-of-sale services on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean rating of respondents on the effect of point of sale services on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State

S/n	Item statements	N	Mean (\bar{X})	Decision
1	It provides convenient location of service facility	270	3.57	Agree
2	Transaction privacy can be easily maintained.	270	3.42	Agree
3	Transfer of fund is easier through POS	270	3.71	Agree
4	Effective in facilitating transaction in retail outlets	270	3.55	Agree
5	Improve customers’ relationship via personalized discounts	270	3.82	Agree
Cluster Mean			3.62	Agree

Analysis in Table 2 showed the mean ratings of respondents on the effect of point-of-sale services on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. The analysis indicated that point of sale services provides

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convenient location of service facility, maintain transaction privacy, easy transfer of funds through POS, effective in facilitating transaction in retail outlets and improve customers’ relationship via personalized discounts with the mean ratings of 3.57, 3.42, 3.71, 3.55 and 3.82 respectively in satisfying customers in commercial banks in Anambra State. The findings revealed that respondents agreed that point of sale services with the cluster mean rating of 3.62 has a positive effect on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Mobile banking services has no significant effect on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.

Table 3: Paired sample t-test of respondents on the significant effect of mobile banking services no customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State

Variables	N	Mean	df	p-value
mobile banking services - customers’ satisfaction	270	3.39	269	0.000

**Significant at $p < .05$*

Analysis in Table 3 showed the paired sample t-test of respondents on the significant effect of mobile banking services no customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. The result showed that p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ level of significance which resulted in the decision to reject the null hypothesis that mobile banking services has no significant effect on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State at $p(0.000) < 0.05$ and accept the alternative hypothesis that mobile banking services has positive significant effect on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Mobile banking services has no significant effect on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.

Table 4: Paired sample t-test of respondents on the significant effect of point of sale services no customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State

Variables	N	Mean	df	p-value
point of sale services - customers’ satisfaction	270	3.62	269	0.000

**Significant at $p < .05$*

Analysis in Table 4 showed the paired sample t-test of respondents on the significant effect of point-of-sale services no customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. The result showed that p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ level of significance which resulted in the decision to reject the null hypothesis that point of sale services has no significant effect on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State at $p(0.000) < 0.05$ and accept the alternative hypothesis that point of sale services has positive significant effect on customers’ satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.

Discussion of the Findings

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Findings on the effect of mobile banking services on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State revealed that mobile banking services exhibit a positive effect on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State with the mean value of 3.39. This implies that improvement in the practices of mobile banking services will bring about increases in customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. The study also revealed that mobile banking services have a significant effect on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. The findings of the study supported the findings of Simon and Thomas (2016) that the convenience of mobile banking positively affects customers' satisfaction to a great. This also agrees with the findings of Rangsang and Titida (2013) that mobile banking has significant impact on customers' satisfaction in banking sectors. This also agrees with the findings of Ogunlowore and Oladele (2014) that there is a significant relationship between electronic banking and customers' satisfaction in the commercial banks. Again, the findings of Mutinda (2014) revealed a positive correlation between mobile banking services and customers' satisfaction in the banking services. Similarly, Kirigano et al. (2016) findings revealed that mobile banking services positively influence customers' satisfaction in the banking sectors.

Findings on the effect of point-of-sale services on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State revealed that point-of-sale services exhibit a positive effect on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State with the mean value of 3.62. This implies that advancement in the practices of point-of-sale services will bring about increases in customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. The study also revealed that point-of-sale services has a significant effect on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State. The finding of this study agrees with the findings of Ahmed et al. (2015) that there is a significant and positive relationship between e-banking factors and customers' satisfactions. The finding tallies with Njenga and Shale (2017) that point-of-sale services has a significant positive effect on customers' satisfaction in the banking activities. The study also agrees with Ugwueze and Nwezeaku (2016) that POS is not integrated with both the savings and time deposits but is integrated with demand deposits. The finding also tallies with Omotayo and Dahunsi (2015) that point-of-sale services has a significant positive effect on customers' satisfaction in banking industries.

Conclusion

The study has shown that electronic banking services are good drivers for ensuring good banking experience and customers' satisfaction in commercial banks. Therefore, the study concluded that electronic banking services have a positive and significant effect on customers' satisfaction in commercial banks in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the study recommends that:

1. Banks should give high priority to customers' service delivery and consider mobile banking as important key drivers towards successful implementation of customers' service delivery. It is therefore important that banks constantly improve and upgrade their e-banking system's security in order to reduce the security threat to the system.

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2. Banking institutions should work hand in hand with major retail outlets and other organizations that use point of sale systems so as to ensure the cards issued to customers and point of sale systems are useful, reliable and can work with speed.

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